

A Rapid Highly Selective Spectrophotometric Determination of Molybdenum(VI) using 5,7-Diiodo-8-hydroxyquinoline

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Oxine and its derivatives have been used for spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum(VI, V) in acidic aqueous media and after extraction of the complex in non-aqueous solvents¹, but the methods suffer from many disadvantages. Here we report a better reagent 5,7-diiodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (DIHQ) for spectrophotometric determination of Mo^{VI} especially in respect of selectivity and sensitivity.

Results and Discussion

Molybdenum(VI) formed a yellow precipitate with DIHQ in acid media which was highly soluble in chloroform and showed an absorption maximum at 397 nm. Beer's law range, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be 0–23 ppm, $0.9738 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.00985 \mu\text{g Mo cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The complex was quantitatively extracted in a single contact with 10 ml each of chloroform and toluene giving the same value of molar absorptivity but the colour was found to be more stable in chloroform (more than one week) than in toluene (2 h) and hence former was preferred in this system. A maximum and constant absorbance was observed in the acidity range 0.01–0.3 M HCl for 1.2–2.5 ml of 0.01 M DIHQ when 10 ml aqueous phase was equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) for 30–300 s. The stoichiometry of the extracted species was found to be 1 : 2 (metal : ligand).

Effect of diverse ions : To test the tolerance limits, 10 $\mu\text{g Mo}$ per ml was determined in presence of respective foreign ions (mg ml⁻¹ in parenthesis). Sulphate, chloride, acetate, nitrate, thiourea, ascorbic acid, bromide and iodide (10 each); borate and thiocyanate (5 each); disodium EDTA (4); fluoride (0.4); glycerol and hydrogen peroxide 20 volume (0.1 ml each) caused < 1% error. Oxalate (0.1) lowered the absorbance by < 5%. Cations such as Ba^{II}, Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, Sr^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Th^{IV}, U^{VI}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} (1 each); W^{VI} (0.5); Se^{IV} and Pb^{II} (0.2 each); Re^{VII}, Bi^{III} and As^{III} (0.1 each); Al^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Pt^{IV}, Ir^{III}, Os^{VIII}, Ta^V, Ag^I, Nb^V and Ru^{III} (0.01 each) and Pd^{II} (0.005) had no effect on the absorbance of Mo^{VI}-DIHQ complex. Cu^{II} (1 in presence of thiourea, 10); Fe^{III} and Cr^{VI} (0.4 and 0.2 respectively, in presence of ascorbic acid, 10); Zr^{IV} (0.1 in presence of NaF, 0.4); V^V (0.02 in presence of both ascorbic acid, 10 and Na₂EDTA, 4) and Sn^{II} (0.01 in presence of sodium tartrate, 1.5) did not interfere. Sb^{III} (0.05) and

Au^{III} (0.01) were extracted considerably (40% each), but both of them did not interfere in the proposed method.

Application : The applicability and usefulness of the method were tested by the satisfactory analysis of steels and reverberatory flue dust. The results obtained were : reverberatory flue dust (Mo added 50, 100 μg , found 49.6, 99.2 μg); BCS 406/1 (Mo 1%, found 0.953%); BCS 219/4 (Mo 0.58%, found 0.56%) and BCS 261/1 (Mo 0.11%, found 0.112%) (average of triplicate analyses).

The method is simple, rapid and had a good precision and accuracy with a relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.69\%$ for ten replicate determinations of $10 \mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$. The method has a better sensitivity ($0.00985 \mu\text{g Mo cm}^{-2}$ giving 0.001 absorbance value) as compared to that using 8-hydroxyquinoline (0.12), 8-mercaptoquinoline (0.0112), 5,7-dibromo-8-hydroxyquinoline (0.0124), 8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (ferron) (0.0174)¹ and a wider Beer's law range¹.

Experimental

A Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched cells was used. Solutions of Mo^{VI} and other ions were prepared as reported earlier². A 0.01 M solution of 5,7-diiodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (Aldrich, purity 97%) was prepared in acetone. Chloroform (Qualigens 'SQ') was distilled and the fraction distilling at 60–61° was used for extraction.

Steel (0.1 g) sample was dissolved as reported earlier³ and the final solution was made 100 ml in 0.1 M HCl; 3 ml (BCS 406/1 and BCS 261/1) or 4 ml (BCS 219/4) aliquots were analysed for Mo after adding 100 mg ascorbic acid in each case before the addition of DIHQ. Reverberatory flue dust sample (0.1 g) from copper manufacture, containing no molybdenum, was mixed with solution of known Mo content (5 mg) and dried in an oven. The dried dust sample was brought into solution as reported earlier³. The filtrate was adjusted to 0.1 M HCl in 100 or 50 ml volume. Molybdenum was determined by the proposed method in aliquot (1 ml) after adding thiourea (100 mg) before the addition of the reagent.

Procedure : To a sample solution containing $\leq 230 \mu\text{g Mo}$, were added 2 ml each of 1 M HCl and 0.01 M DIHQ, and the volume was adjusted to 10 ml with deionised wa-

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ter. After mixing, the content was equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) for 1 min. The separated yellow coloured organic phase was passed through filter paper to remove water droplets and its absorbance was measured at 397 nm against a reagent blank. Molybdenum content in the samples was computed from a calibration curve prepared as per the proposed method.

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